

PSSOH 2026 Conference Agenda

Date: June 26, 2026

Place: amfiteater 56, building of Technical faculties ([University of Belgrade – School of Electrical Engineering](#)), ground floor, Bulevar kralja Aleksandra 73, 11000 Belgrade, Serbia

CET	Lecturer	Talk
PSSOH Introductory Session		
10:00-10:05	ETF Dean Prof. Zoran Čiča	Welcome Note
10:05-10:20	PSSOH Editor Prof. Nadica Miljković	The Eight PSSOH: Editorial Board Perspective
PSSOH Session I with Invited Lectures Moderator: PSSOH Editor Assoc. Prof. Miloš Bjelić		
10:20-10:40	Aleksandar Sekulić and Milan Kilibarda	Spatial Interpolation in R: The RFSI Method
10:40-11:00	Vladimir Otašević, Ana Bošković, Slađana Savić Jovanović, and Marija Ristić	Monitoring Research Assessment and the Evaluation of Open Science at a Faculty of Chemistry
11:00-11:20	Ilija Tanasković, Nadica Miljković, and Matija Zlatar	Toward Reproducible Machine Learning Pipelines in Medical Applications
11:20-11:40	Short Break	
11:40-12:00	Miloš Rašić	DEMO - Inside a Blood Pressure Monitor: Designing Open-Source Hardware for Understanding Cardiography Measurements
PSSOH Session II with Invited Lectures Moderator: PSSOH Editor Assoc. Prof. Miloš Bjelić		
12:00-12:20	Haris Turkmanović, Filip Radojević, Ivan Popović, and Vladimir Rajović	An Open-Source Hardware-Software Framework for Algorithm Evaluation in Battery-Powered Embedded Systems
12:20-12:40	Obrad Vučkovic, Vladimir Otašević, Marija Ristić, and Slavko Gajin	More Efficient Research from Day One: A Practical Roadmap to Managing and Sharing Your Data
12:40-13:00	Sara Đorđević and Bratislav Iričanin	From Classical Computational Framework to AI-enhanced Learning Tool for Special Mathematical Functions — Design and Implementation
13:00-13:05	PSSOH Editor Assoc. Prof. Miloš Cvetanović	Conference Closing
13:05-14:00	Brunch Break and Networking	

